

**TYPES OF INTEGRATED LESSONS. EFFECTIVENESS
OF ORGANIZING INTEGRATED LESSONS****Muratkhodjayeva Ziyoda Bakhtiyarovna****Nizami Uzbek State University of Education, Faculty of Preschool and
Primary Education, Department of Primary Education Pedagogy,
Associate Professor****muratkhodjayevaziyoda7@gmail.com +998909575501****Shamshidinova Dilsabo Munavvarjon kizi****4th year student of the Nizami Uzbek State University of Education,
Faculty of Preschool and Primary Education****shamshidinovadilsabo0204@gmail.com +998995043727****Kochkorova Hilola Said kizi****4th year student of the Nizami Uzbek State University of Education,
Faculty of Preschool and Primary qochqorovahilola@gmail.com****+998932228220****Sobirova Rayhona Bakhtiyor kizi****Nizami Uzbek State University of Education, Faculty of Preschool and
Primary Education 4th grade student****rayhona189@gmail.com****+998954879705****Shamsiddinova Shahina Bakhtiyor kizi****4th grade student of the Faculty of Preschool and Primary Education of
the Nizami State University of Uzbekistan****shamsiddinovashahinabobu@gmail.com****+998970840052****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19598214>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 01st April 2026Accepted: 04th April 2026Online: 06th April 2026**KEYWORDS***digitization, modern education,
teacher-student relations,
teaching***ABSTRACT***This article lists the advantages of digitalization, which is becoming a modern requirement. At the same time, in the digital education system, the teacher-student relationship reveals that it plays a very important role and influence in the educational process.***Introduction**

Today, the education system is aimed not only at teaching students the basics of science, but also at educating individuals who can expand their thinking, understand the world as a whole, and correctly analyze the essence of the events surrounding them. One of the priority tasks of modern education is to form students from a young age as independent thinkers and individuals ready for life, without excessive mental stress.

The isolated (scattered) presentation of subjects taught at school provides the student with only a narrow range of theoretical knowledge. Such knowledge is lost from memory over time and does not find its expression in practice. Therefore, scientists recognize integration as one of the leading didactic principles. The role of integrated lessons in the comprehensive development of the mental activity of primary school students is incomparable. Currently,

about 70 percent of developed countries effectively use integrated curricula and textbooks in their education systems. In particular:

In the UK, mainly integrative subjects have been introduced;

In South Korea and Switzerland, lessons based on interdisciplinary harmony are a priority;

In Hungary, cultural subjects are taught as a whole;

In Ireland, science and technology blocks are integrated with all academic subjects.

Pedagogue U. Musayev emphasizes the need for integration to present topics sequentially and in a logical connection. In this case, the principle of concentricity is followed when presenting educational materials, that is, the previously learned knowledge complements and deepens the subsequent one.

As noted in the work "Analysis of the Modern Lesson" by T.T. Lakotsenina and S.V. Kulnevich: "Integration is the systematic introduction and unification of generalized knowledge in a certain area into one educational material as much as possible."

Literature analysis and research methodology

The word "integration" comes from the Latin *integratio* - restoration, completion, "integer" - whole. The concept of integration is interpreted as the following two processes:

Firstly, the concept of the state of connection of separately differentiated parts and functions of a system, organism, and the process leading to this state;

Secondly, the process of rapprochement of disciplines, which is carried out along with the processes of differentiation.

Genetically, integration is a logically completed form and level of content, synthesizing the content of subjects at least at the level of educational standards, combining continuity, intersubject connection, interrelationship, and finally complementing each other, expanding and deepening each other. Because each lower level of intersubject connection is established between certain didactic units within the studied subjects, and it provides for the coordination of the content and terms of their study. In contrast, an educational subject organized on the basis of integrative connection or an integrated study of the subject, phenomena or processes in the form of a holistic system requires an interpretation of all-round connections and relationships.

Integration is the opposite of differentiation and is a process that is opposite to it. It can be implemented in the following areas:

a) integrated study of content within subjects and disciplines;

b) integration of the activities of teachers of different subjects;

c) integration of forms of organization of educational work or the school day.

Currently, in primary education pedagogy, there is a process of finding more effective ways of education. Pedagogical integration is one of such ways, and one of its foundations is integrated lessons.

Integrative lessons are an interactive educational system that studies the secrets of creating visual skills based on deepening and expanding integrative knowledge. The formation of various types of thinking skills in primary school students is the basis of integration. Integrated lessons teach children to naturally understand the unity of the

worldview, the continuity of events. In integrative lessons, topics and activities are taught collaboratively, with the participation of specialists and with the activity of students.

There are 5 main goals of integrative lessons:

Developing the mental and emotional abilities of students;

Developing the will of students;

Developing the individual character of students;

Increasing students' interest in other subjects;

Forming research skills in students.

Interdisciplinary integration is manifested in the use of material from one subject when studying another. The systematization of the content carried out at this level leads to the formation of a holistic image of the object being studied in the minds of students.

3 types of integrated lessons are currently popular:

1. Auction lesson;

2. Innovation lesson;

3. Collaboration lesson.

Auction lesson - a brief explanation of specific topics is given, students' opinions are studied and they are evaluated by a specialist. In such a lesson, students are divided into four groups and group members present their opinions on the given topics. The group whose opinion covers the topic most comprehensively is the winner, and each of the group members is evaluated equally. At the end of the auction lesson, homework is not given.

Collaboration lesson - is based on the presentation of specific topics with the participation of specialists. In it, the specialist explains the topic in the form of a lecture and answers students' questions at the end of the lesson. The teacher assesses the knowledge of students based on their participation in the discussion. In modern primary education, it is recommended to organize a cooperative lesson once a quarter.

An innovative lesson is an important component of integrated education, which involves introducing new pedagogical technologies and modern methods into the lesson process. In such lessons, the student becomes not just a receiver of ready-made information, but an active creator of the lesson. The uniqueness of an innovative lesson is that interdisciplinary connections are implemented through problem situations, game technologies and information media. This expands the scope of independent thinking of students, develops their ability to strive for innovation and find non-standard solutions. This form of the lesson serves as the main tool for forming the above-mentioned research skills and revealing the individual character of students.

Discussion and results

Extensive discussions on the types of integrated lessons and their effectiveness in the educational process confirm that this approach is one of the most promising areas of modern pedagogy. The main emphasis in the discussion is on removing artificial barriers between subjects and presenting the world to the student as a whole, not as a fragmented reality. When models such as auction and cooperative lessons are implemented in practice, students are observed to transform from passive listeners to active researchers in the lesson. This puts the personal development of the student, not the teacher, at the center of the pedagogical process. The results show that integrated lessons significantly increase the cognitive abilities

of students, since when the brain logically connects information from several disciplines at once, the level of memory retention and comprehension is higher. The participation of specialists in cooperative lessons begins to form the professional worldview of students from the very first stage and ensures the continuity of theoretical knowledge with real-life practice. At the same time, such lessons strengthen the will and individual character of the student, because in an integrative environment the child is forced to apply the acquired knowledge in unfamiliar situations, which increases his self-confidence.

The most important among the indicators of effectiveness is the improvement of the quality of education, as well as the decrease in the level of student fatigue. Combining repetitive information from different subjects in one block saves study time and provides the depth of the lesson. As a result, flexibility of thinking is formed in primary school students, which allows them to systematically analyze complex scientific problems in the future. Such lessons, which are manifested as the highest form of pedagogical integration, serve as the most optimal means of not only fulfilling educational standards, but also instilling them in the student's personality.

The methodological basis of integrated lessons is that they prevent the fragmentation of knowledge in the student's mind and show the place of each concept being studied in the worldview. It was especially noted in the discussions that the role of the teacher in such lessons also changes radically - he is no longer just a provider of information, but becomes a creative moderator who creates a synthesis of knowledge at the intersection of different disciplines. Since figurative thinking is especially strong in primary school children, an integrated approach ensures long-term and strong retention of the lesson topic in their memory. An analysis of practical results shows that integrated types of lessons, in particular, auction and innovative lessons, increase students' speech culture and the ability to draw logical conclusions. Cooperative lessons, on the other hand, give a social color to the educational environment and form a sense of teamwork and mutual assistance in students. This process ensures not only the intellectual, but also the social maturity of students.

As a result, the effectiveness of the lesson is measured not only by the acquired grades, but also by the child's ability to connect life events and independently analyze cause and effect relationships. Pedagogical integration, along with enriching the content of education, encourages constant updating of teaching methods, which guarantees that primary education meets modern requirements. Also, such a high level of inter-class continuity increases the psychological resilience of students and prepares them to find the right direction in the flow of complex information.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in an environment where interdisciplinary connections are provided, along with the increase in the level of knowledge of students, their cognitive abilities, intellectual potential and interest in science are significantly increased. The organization of integrated lessons in primary education is not just a modern methodological technique, but a strategic pedagogical necessity that radically improves the quality of education. This approach serves to form a holistic and interconnected picture of the world in the mind of the student, not a fragmented one. Research and practical experience show that interdisciplinary integration, as a process opposed to differentiation, logically systems educational materials,

which in turn develops analytical thinking and complex problem-solving skills in students from an early age.

Types of integrated lessons such as auction, collaboration and innovation abandon traditional lesson patterns and make the student the central subject of the lesson. In such lessons, students not only master theoretical knowledge, but also increase their social competencies by applying it in different situations, working in teams, and communicating with specialists. This process develops not only the intellectual potential of the student, but also his will and emotional qualities. The involvement of specialists and the connection of lessons with real-life events increase students' interest in science and instill in them the spirit of independent research. In addition, the integrated education system is highly effective in the efficient use of study time and the prevention of psychophysiological stress in students. The combination of similar topics in different disciplines in a single didactic block eliminates repetition and ensures a more in-depth study of topics. As a final result, it can be said that pedagogical integration is the most optimal and effective way to achieve the highest goals set by national educational standards, namely the formation of a comprehensively mature, logically thinking and competitive personality. Therefore, the systematic implementation of integrated lessons remains one of the most important tasks facing modern primary education.

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